

Electronic Supplementary Material

Modulating lifetime distribution through variable excitation pulse length and power: a case study on colloidal PbS quantum dots

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Relation between the PbS Qdot band gap and the particle size

Figure S1. Relationship between optical emission (left axis) and absorption (right axis) peaks and the quantum dot diameter. Dashed brown and green curves are plotted according to equations by Moreels et al. [7] and Reilly et al. [8], respectively. Solid lines are polynomial approximations of the data provided by the QD producer. Red and blue dashed arrows indicate the corresponding axes for the data points. Dotted lines denote the parameters of the studied sample.

Estimation of the particle size distribution

Quantum Solutions™ provides two series of PbS samples: absorption and emission types which are based on either absorption or emission characteristics. In the brochure "QDot™ PbS Quantum Dots: TEM Images and Particle Size Distribution" by Quantum Solutions™, the variation of the mean PbS particle size (absorption type) as a function of the absorption peak is presented. This data has been replotted in Fig. S2 as green points, along with its quadratic fit. Since our sample belongs to the emission type, it is essential to compare both the absorption and emission series on the same plot. From Fig. S2, it can be observed that both series are nearly identical, differing only within a margin of reproducibility error.

Figure S2. Relationship between absorption peaks and the quantum dot diameter. The black dashed line is plotted according to equation by Moreels et al. [7]. Green dots and blue squares show Passport experimental points for absorption and emission series, respectively. The green and blue dashed lines show quadratic polynomial approximations of the corresponding data points.

The same brochure also includes histograms of particle size distributions obtained from TEM images. We focus on two samples, QDot™ PbS-800-abs and QDot™ PbS-920-abs, with absorption peaks at 785 nm and 934 nm, respectively, as these are closest to our sample. According to the emission (and absorption) series in Fig. S2, these peaks correspond to sizes of approximately 2.7 nm (2.8 nm) and 3.3 nm (3.5 nm), respectively. The absorption peak near 746 nm for our sample corresponds to a size of about 2.6 nm, as indicated in Fig. S1 and Fig. S2. We adjusted the histograms for the two reference samples by 0.15 nm and 0.95 nm, respectively, to align their mean sizes with our sample's mean size, as shown in Fig. S3.

Figure S3. Histograms of normalized QD size distribution for samples corresponding to emission peaks at 785 nm (orange bars) and 934 nm (blue bars) according to the brochure "QDot™ PbS Quantum Dots. TEM images and particle size distribution" by Quantum Solutions™. The data has been adjusted to match the mean size of 2.6 nm for our sample.

The normalized histograms are quite similar, with the QDot™ PbS-800-abs sample showing a slightly lower count of small particles and a higher count of larger particles compared to the QDot™ PbS-920-abs sample. Fig. S3 provides a realistic representation of the particle size distribution in our sample, where particle sizes range between ~2.0 nm and 3.3 nm.

Rough estimation of ACS from absorbance

Absorbance can be calculated using the following equation:

$$A = -\log_{10}(T) = -\log_{10}\left(\frac{I}{I_0}\right) = -\log_{10}\left(\frac{I^* + (R + S)}{I_0}\right) \quad (\text{S1})$$

where A and T represent absorbance and transmittance, respectively, and I_0 and I denote the intensities of the incident and transmitted light, I^* is the intensity of the transmitted light that would have been observed if only absorption occurred, while R and S account for reflection and scattering, respectively.

In this estimation, we assume $I \approx I^*$, as no separate experimental data is available for R and S parameters. As a result, A will likely be overestimated, though this overestimation should not be large for small particle sizes.

In principle, the ACS can be estimated from absorbance using the equation:

$$A = \sigma c_v l \quad (\text{S2})$$

where σ is the ACS, c_v is the volume concentration of particles, l is the optical path length.

The major issue in Eq. (S2) is that we don't know the exact value for c_v . However, we can attempt a rough estimate of c_v from the absorbance near 400 nm following the method described in ref. [14] of the paper. Since we do not have absorbance data below 500 nm, we extrapolated the data (see Fig. S4, red curve). The extrapolated absorbance at 400 nm is approximately 1.023 and most probably is overestimated due to extrapolation.

Figure S4. Absorbance of the sample showing experimental data (dark cyan line) and extrapolated experimental values (red line). Both linear and B-Spline extrapolations yield the same result. The absorbance at 400 nm is marked with dashed-dotted lines.

The volume concentration can be estimated using the following equation:

$$c_V \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3} \right] = \frac{c_V \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{L}} \right]}{1000} = \frac{A_{400}}{22.4 \cdot 10^6 \cdot l[\text{cm}] \cdot (d[\text{nm}])^3} \frac{1}{1 - e^{-0.443d}} \quad (\text{S3})$$

Combining Eq. (S2) with Eq. (S3), yields:

$$\sigma = \frac{A}{c_V \left[\frac{1}{\text{cm}^3} \right] l[\text{cm}]} = \frac{A}{N_A \left[\frac{1}{\text{mol}} \right] \cdot c_V \left[\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3} \right] l[\text{cm}]} = \frac{A}{A_{400}} \cdot \frac{22.4 \cdot 10^6 \cdot d^3 \cdot (1 - e^{-0.443d})}{N_A} \quad (\text{S4})$$

Using the extrapolated absorbance data $A_{400} = 1.023$ and known particle mean size $d = 2.6$, we calculate the absorption cross section, as shown in Fig. S5.

Figure S5. Calculated absorption cross section of the sample from absorbance using Eq. (S4). The cross-section at 532 nm is indicated by dashed-dotted lines.

At the excitation wavelength 532 nm, the high-level estimate of ACS is approximately $1.7 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$, which is reasonably close to the value obtained using PL lifetime modulation in this study. We consider this agreement satisfactory, especially given the assumptions made, including the omission of reflection and scattering effects as well as extrapolation of absorbance data which likely lead to an overestimation of the ACS values derived from absorbance measurements.